

THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING CONTENT IN LEARNING ENGLISH SPEECH

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Abstract:

This article discusses the content and importance of teaching English in technical universities.

Key words: pedagogical skills, learning content, self-study, linguistic methodology, association

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Interdisciplinary communication is of great importance in teaching English or any other subject. At a time when rapid changes are taking place in various fields and international political, economic and cultural ties are becoming increasingly thick, it means that we need to master foreign languages in a deep, wide and perfect way. We also increase the effectiveness of education only if every teacher in the field of education, using their knowledge and pedagogical skills, uses them in practical experiences, based on their own circumstances.

The teaching of a foreign language in technical universities requires a new natural approach. The content of teaching English speech is organized under the following names for 1st, 2nd, 3rd courses: Topics, Lexics, Grammar, Pronunciation, Listening, Speaking, Reading, Writing, Crosscultural, Self-study. reflects.

Speech requires the ability to use language material to express an idea or to understand an expressed idea. To achieve this, a strong and flexible connection, an association, must be established between the means of language and the content of speech. Three-step methodological skills are used in practice to build lexical skills:

1. The presentation phase consists of introducing a new lexical unit and performing its initial lexical actions;
2. Perform lexical exercises. This stage is mainly focused on skill building;
3. The stage of application of the lexical phenomenon in the types of speech activities. Lexical skills are used in speech and work is done to turn them into skills.

Vocabulary serves to shape skills, not to absorb knowledge. One of the most important issues is to determine the level of lexical skills and speaking skills acquired by students of technical universities in English and to determine the program requirements in this area. Students have a certain level of knowledge, skills and competencies in English and need to improve them again.

Within the context of a technical university, students first learn the abstract concept and simple rules of foreign language phenomena and, secondly, the information expressed through that language. In the process of learning English speech, students receive not only knowledge but also education. Their cognitive

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activity is increased and their spiritual needs for language are met. Students achieve spiritual maturity by comprehending (reading / listening) English texts in class and exchanging information (receiving / giving) in comprehension (speaking / writing). Depending on the facts of general and specific linguistics, the typology of difficulties associated with the phenomenon of interlingual interference is determined, and the selection and organization of educational material is carried out. Linguistic information about the central role of the word in the language system, based on information from the theory of speech activity, confirms that it plays a key role in the reception and transmission of information in speech. Both attitudes are important for being able to speak a language: the first ensures that words in that group are selected according to their meaning, and the second ensures that they are connected correctly when used in a sentence. The solution of this whole set of problems is related to linguistics, the nature of the language material, the concept of language and speech, their interrelationships and functions, language contacts.

The essence of the goal is to develop the mental (educational), emotional (educational) and motivational (speech tendencies) aspects of students of technical universities. As for the content of foreign language teaching, its components are defined in lingovomethodics: (1) speech topics included in the program, (2) speaking skills and competencies, and (3) language material. The institute provides general information about the phonetic side of the language, grammatical structure and vocabulary, depending on the age and level of knowledge of students. It is in connection with this knowledge that the norms of writing and stylistics are taught. The content and scope of these are determined in the foreign language subject programs, and their content is described in textbooks. Vocabulary training, especially vocabulary training, should be explained in relation to social events and changes in life. In this case, the teacher should use the materials of the local press and fiction.

The topics selected for teaching English in technical universities include, in general, (1) "Our Institute", (2) "My Specialty" and (3) "Cultural Capitals of Uzbekistan".

In the case of specialization in any field, in addition, another topic is included under the title "Future specialization of students."

Conclusion.

In this case, the task of teaching / learning sectoral terminology is also set. Terms are selected separately for each Technical University, for example, chemistry, mathematics, physics, etc. Being able to communicate in English in their field of specialization, understanding and responding to the opinions of others (orally / in writing), in turn, requires more independent work and research in practice.

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